

DEVELOPMENT OF THE LEGAL SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article analyzes the important historical and legal documents that served to ensure the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the formation and development stages of the legal system of the country, the prospects for the development of the legislation of our independent state. The changes in the social, economic, political, legal and cultural life of the country are reflected in the legal system.

Key words: Independence of Uzbekistan, the Declaration of Independence, the Constitution and laws, the legal system of society and its stages of development, the priorities of legal development.

Uzbekistan's independent development has a solid legal basis. The fact that the democratic rule of law and civil society being built in our country serve the individual and his or her development is enshrined in our Constitution and laws. During the years of independence, the legal system of our state has gradually developed. It has gradually changed in line with the social, economic, political, and cultural development of society. The analysis of the period of our independent development shows that the legal framework of society is mobilized at each stage to address the priorities of society and the state. These stages will serve as an important foundation for the formation of our statehood and legal system. It is known that the normative basis of the national legal system is the Constitution, laws and other normative legal acts. Today Lex. A total of 99,706 documents are included in the national legislation, including 1,228 decrees, (including 6 constitutional decrees, 18 codes), 5,749 presidential decrees, 7,377 presidential

resolutions, 28,296 government resolutions and normative legal acts of 22130 ministries and state committees were adopted. The legal development of our country during the years of independence can be conditionally studied in 4 stages. The first covers the transition period and the stage of formation of the foundations of national statehood - 1991-2000. From the first days of independence, building a democratic state governed by the rule of law and a civil society based on a socially oriented market economy was identified as the target. The Declaration of Independence was a historically important step in laying the foundation stone of a statehood in Uzbekistan based on advanced democratic principles. On June 20, 1990, the second session of the Supreme Soviet of the XII convocation unanimously adopted the Declaration of Independence of Uzbekistan. In it, the Supreme Soviet of the Soviet Socialist Republic of Uzbekistan adheres to the rules of international law, universal values and the deepest sense of historical responsibility for the future of Uzbekistan. The declaration of state independence of the Soviet Socialist Republic of Uzbekistan based on the principles of democracy was strengthened. On August 31, 1991, the XII Extraordinary Session of the Supreme Soviet of Uzbekistan published the "Declaration of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Uzbekistan on State Independence". The Resolution "On the Declaration of State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the decree "On the Foundations of State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan" were adopted. In its Declaration, the Supreme Soviet declared the state independence of Uzbekistan and the establishment of a free sovereign state - the Republic of Uzbekistan. The free and independent people of the Republic of Uzbekistan were recognized as the sole owners of state power. The exercise of state power, both directly and through a system of representative bodies, has been strengthened. The Law "On the Foundations of State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan" is the foundation of our independence and has great political and historical significance. It consists of 17 articles, which strengthen the main features of state sovereignty. Under this law, the legal status of Uzbekistan has changed

radically. In particular, the first article of the law declared the Republic of Uzbekistan an independent democratic republic.

In a historically short period of time, our Basic Law - the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan - has been developed and adopted. The Constitution is a high-ranking legal document that embodies the best practices and ideas of mankind in the field of democratic statehood, a just legal system and the rule of law, as well as universal and national values. The most important principles of social justice, democracy, human rights, separation of powers, the rule of law and civil society have a worthy place in it. The achievements of our people for thousands of years of statehood and legal development, its age-old aspirations for freedom, liberty and independence are reflected. In the first stage, our national legal system was formed, which has a completely new meaning. In a short period of time, a number of traditional and new branches of law have been established and developed in parallel with the changes in the legislation. In particular, civil law, labor law, family law, land law, water law, environmental law, financial law, administrative law, criminal law, criminal executive law, criminal procedural law, civil procedural law, economic procedural law. industries, as well as new branches of law such as business law, customs law, corporate law, banking law, tax law, international law

Some of the president's powers have been transferred to the upper house, the Senate. The rights and powers of the Prime Minister have been expanded. In 2007, the country passed a law abolishing the death penalty and transferring the power to issue arrest warrants from the prosecutor's office to the courts. As a result of the liberalization of the penitentiary system, about 75% of serious and very serious crimes have been transferred to the category of lowrisk crimes. The Institute of Reconciliation was introduced. Following these changes, the number of sentences imposed by the courts in 2006 decreased by 20% compared to 2000. At this stage, as before, some legislative acts regulating social life have become declarative. The adopted laws do not pay enough attention to the analysis of the social mechanism

of law enforcement, the issues of sociological support of lawmaking, the social factors of law enforcement. The third stage, 2010-2016, is the concept of further deepening democratic reforms and development of civil society in the country and the stage of its implementation. The concept identifies priorities for the future development of our society. At the same time, in solving important tasks in this area, further development and strengthening of public authorities, in particular, the parliament, increasing the role of political parties, improving the judicial system and electoral legislation, development of civil society institutions, media, as well as democratic reforms. A number of legislative initiatives aimed at further deepening and liberalizing the economy were put forward. In the process of implementing the Concept, about fifty laws have been adopted in accordance with the principles and provisions of our Constitution, or the necessary amendments and additions have been made to existing laws. In the third stage of legal development, the issues of establishing effective control mechanisms for the protection of constitutional rights, improving the procedure for restoring violated rights of citizens, and improving the procedure for dealing with complaints of violations of constitutional rights remained unresolved. The fourth phase covers the period from 2017 to the present. This is the strategy of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 in our country and the period of its implementation. The consistent implementation of the rules and objectives set out in the Action Strategy, which was announced five years ago, is bearing fruit. As result, Uzbekistan was able to show high performance in a number of international indices. In particular, Uzbekistan ranked 44th in the Open Data Monitor International Index, rising 125 places. At the same time, it is important to introduce the practice of disclosure of indicators in 20 areas of public administration. The essence of the unprecedented reforms in society and public administration was the idea put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev: “People shouldn’t serve government, they should serve local people”. onal economic and trade ties. Thus, the independent

development of the Republic of Uzbekistan has a solid legal basis, which has developed gradually in line with the social, economic, political and cultural development of society. The development of the legal system in accordance with the requirements of society will allow our country to take its rightful place among the world community, to guarantee human rights and freedoms, and to accelerate economic growth.

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